

Design of Portable Biosensor Reader for Leptospira Detection

(Reka Bentuk Pembaca Biosensor Mudah alih untuk Pengesanan Leptospira)

Kaliswaran a/l Ganesan, Noorfazila Kamal*, Huda Abdullah

Department of Electrical, Electronic and Systems Engineering
Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Malaysia

*Corresponding author: fazila@ukm.edu.my

ABSTRACT

Leptospirosis is a chronic disease caused by leptospira bacteria that affects risk groups exposed to animal waste reservoirs or contaminated environments. It will cause several health complications such as kidney failure, jaundice, and internal bleeding to humans. Leptospirosis has emerged as a health threat in a new state due to the influence of globalization and climate. The cause of leptospira infection will only be investigated after a case is confirmed or death from leptospirosis. Currently available techniques for leptospira detection are largely limited to the laboratory and require large and expensive instruments to perform the analysis. Therefore, to overcome this problem, this study designed a portable biosensor reader that uses potentiostats for on-site leptospira detection. This biosensor reader uses a linear sweep voltammetry electroanalytic method for detection. This project is divided into two phases which is designing a portable voltammetric potentiostat and designing an on-site leptospira detection system. In the first phase, a voltammetric potentiostat was designed using Proteus Design Suite software. The potentiostat is designed using a microcontroller as a voltage supplier and a current reader, then the operational amplifier circuit operates as a voltage and current transfer to the electrode. On the part of the leptospira detection system, the microcontroller is programmed to detect the presence of leptospira based on the specifications of the PANI-Fe-Al biosensor. LCD board and an application specially developed for displaying the results of the detection system. The results of this study show that the designed potentiostat can run smoothly and the detection system can detect the presence of leptospira according to the required specifications.

Keywords: Leptospira; Potentiostat; Linear sweep voltammetry; PANI-Fe-Al

ABSTRAK

Leptospirosis merupakan penyakit kronik yang disebabkan oleh bakteria leptospira yang mempengaruhi kumpulan risiko yang terdedah kepada takungan sisa haiwan atau persekitaran yang tercemar. Ia akan menyebabkan beberapa komplikasi kesihatan seperti kegagalan buah pinggang, penyakit kuning dan pendarahan dalaman kepada manusia. Leptospirosis telah muncul sebagai ancaman kesihatan dalam keadaan baru kerana pengaruh globalisasi dan iklim. Punca jangkitan leptospira hanya akan disiasat setelah kes disahkan atau meninggal dunia akibat leptospirosis. Teknik yang ada pada masa ini untuk pengesanan leptospira sebahagian besarnya terbatas pada makmal dan memerlukan instrumen yang besar dan mahal untuk melaksanakan analisis. Oleh itu bagi mengatasi masalah ini, kajian ini mereka bentuk pembaca biosensor mudah alih yang menggunakan potensiostat untuk pengesanan leptospira di lapangan. Pembaca biosensor ini menggunakan kaedah elektroanalitik voltammetri sapuan linear untuk pengesanan. Projek ini dibahagikan kepada dua fasa iaitu merekabentuk potensiostat voltammetrik mudah alih dan merekabentuk sistem pengesanan leptospira di lapangan. Dalam fasa pertama, potensiostat voltammetrik direkabentuk dengan menggunakan perisian Proteus Design Suite. Potensiostat ini direkabentuk dengan menggunakan mikropengawal sebagai pembekal voltan dan pembaca arus, lalu litar penguat operasi sebagai pemindah voltan dan arus ke elektrod. Pada bahagian sistem pengesanan leptospira pula, mikropengawal diaturcara supaya dapat mengesan kehadiran leptospira berdasarkan spesifikasi biosensor PANI-Fe-Al. Papan LCD dan sebuah aplikasidibangunkan khas untuk paparan hasil keputusan sistem pengesanan. Hasil kajian ini menunjukkan, potensiostatyang direkabentuk dapat berjalan lancar dan sistem pengesanan dapat mengesan kehadiran leptospira mengikutspesifikasi yang diperlukan.

Kata Kunci: Leptospira; Potensiostat; Voltammetri sapuan linear; PANI-Fe-Al

INTRODUCTION

The pathogenic *Leptospira* bacteria causes leptospirosis, a widespread zoonotic illness (Nagraik et al., 2019). It is one of the most serious human health issues. The pathogenic strain *Leptospira interrogans* and the nonpathogenic strain or saprophyte *Leptospira biflexa* are the two primary species of *Leptospira* (Adler & de la Peña Moctezuma, 2010). Risk groups exposed to animal waste reservoirs or contaminated surroundings, such as slaughterhouses, sewage employees, military personnel, and people who participate in water sports and enjoyment, are all susceptible to leptospirosis (Costa et al., 2015). In subtropical countries, high tropical humidity and mild temperatures are excellent for *Leptospira* to thrive for lengthy periods of time in the environment (Benacer et al., 2013).

Humans are usually infected with *Leptospira* pathogenic infections after coming into contact with polluted water or soil from diseased animals' urine. It will create several health problems, including kidney failure, jaundice, and internal bleeding, all of which will raise the death rate over time. Controlling zoonotic illnesses, which are diseases passed from animals to humans, has received a lot of attention around the world to date (Jampasa et al., 2019). Due to the influence of globalization and climate change, leptospirosis has become a new health issue (Costa et al., 2015)

The presence of leptospira requires laboratory diagnosis employing fluorescent markers to culture bacteria from blood, urine, and tissues. Standard methods for detecting certain bacteria, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), for use on urine and blood samples include microscopic agglutination test (MAT) and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (Azizi et al., 2014; Vasconcellos et al., 2010). Several approaches can be used to identify leptospira in water, including hybridization probes in Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and Ribonucleic acid (RNA), but this detection method is enhanced since it has a time limit and sensitivity.

After a case of leptospirosis is confirmed or a death due to leptospirosis occurs, the cause of infection will be explored. Preventive interventions are complicated by the lack of a portable leptospira detection system that may be utilized on-site. The existing procedures are mostly limited to laboratory detection, which takes longer and necessitates the use of large, expensive tools to implement advanced analytical systems.

The thin film sensor as shown in Figure 1 works through a biochemical reaction between the thin surface and the content sample, especially bacteria, to describe several accurately measurable electrical values or signals. This response will

introduce certain variations in the value of the detected signal. Electrochemical impedance (EIS) and current voltage ($I - V$) spectroscopic measurements were used to confirm the sensitivity and efficacy of sensors with different concentrations of *Leptospira* bacteria (Jurait et al., 2018).

FIGURE 1: The design of comb- structured silver electrode PANI Fe-Al

As a result, this study designed a portable biosensor reader based on a microcontroller and a potentiostat for on-site leptospira detection. This potentiostat is a miniature potentiostat that can do precise potentiostatic measurements. The voltametric approach, voltage range (V), voltage change rate (V), current measurement range (I), resolution, and sampling rate of the potentiostat will vary depending on the intended device usage. There are many types of voltammetry procedures, such as "linear sweep," "square wave," "cycle voltammetry," and so on.

Identify a viable voltametric technique for leptospira detection, develop a compact voltametric potentiostat for on-site leptospira detection, and design a portable leptospira detection system are the three specific aims for this work. The goal of this study is to design a portable leptospira detection device based on a PANI-Fe-Al nanocomposite thin film sensor in the research (Jurait et al., 2018). The approach for determining the presence of leptospira is derived from oft study's findings in (Jurait et al., 2018).

It is important to detect these pathogens in the environment so that early prevention can be undertaken. This research will address few key techniques and components for design the portable biosensor reader.

Leptospira bacterial detection technique

Because of its high conductivity and ease of control, using a thin film of polyaniline nanocomposites (PANI-Fe-Al) to detect *Leptospira* can improve sensitivity. Because of its high conductivity, compatibility with biological molecules, environmental durability, and ease of synthesis of affordable monomers, polyaniline is a form of conductive polymer with a wide range of uses in

electrochemical biosensors (Thakur et al., 2015). The negative charge of the cell structure of *Leptospira* bacteria will create a reactivity with the thin film surface of PANI-Fe-Al nanocomposites. Spectroscopic measurements of electrochemical impedance (EIS) and current voltage (I-V) were conducted to confirm the sensitivity and effectiveness of these sensor in the research (Jurait et al., 2018). Figure 2 displays the findings of the sensor reaction for the concentration of *Leptospira* bacteria using a leptospira sample (108 CFU mL⁻¹). The current voltage curve (I - V) is obtained using a potentiostat.

FIGURE 2: Measurement of (I-V) PANI-Fe0.8-Al0.2 thin film sensor nanocomposites

Voltammetry

Voltammetry experiments investigate an analyte's half-cell reactivity. For each voltage supplied, the voltammetry method takes a current reading. The voltage is progressively increased or decreased over time, with the exact current value being measured as a dependent variable. The current at a working electrode (WE) is measured when the voltage between the counter electrode (CE) and the reference electrode (RE) is swept linearly during a fixed time interval in linear sweep voltammetry (LSV). The scan rate is the voltage against time graph, and it can range from 1mV to 1,000,000 V/s. (Scholz, 2015).

Portable potentiostat

A portable potentiostat is a customized device that can make accurate potentiostatic measurements in a compact form while keeping the original potentiostat's definition. Several simple electronic components, such as resistors, capacitors, and operational amplifiers (op-amps), can be used to build a rudimentary potentiostat (Meloni et al., 2016). The operating amplifier controls the flow of current through the electrochemical cell through the response electrode (CE) and the working electrode (WE). Because it involves fewer production stages and allows for subsequent adjustments, a microcontroller-based potentiostat design, such as the Arduino, was chosen. Using pulse width modulation (PWM) pin control, Arduino circuit boards generate fixed voltage waveforms. At a

constant frequency, this voltage oscillates between high and low levels. It is possible to create voltage ramps at different scan rates for different electrochemical studies to perform cyclic voltammetry (CV), linear sweep voltammetry (LV), or Chronoamperometry by adjusting the PWM duty cycle.

Biosensor reader

Biosensor readers are made up of bio-receptors (enzymes/antibodies), transducer components (semiconductor materials/nanomaterials), and electronic systems (signal amplifiers, processors, and displays) (Kaur & Shorie, 2019). The operating amplifier (op-amp) of the biosensor reader is connected between the electrode and the probe channel. The biosensor reader examines the voltage and current changes at the electrode generated by the reaction between the electrode and the target substance in the electrochemical solution. A measurement module and an output module are included in the biosensor reader. The measurement module connects the probe channel to a fixed resistance reference resistor on the op-amp, measuring the reference voltage drop in the reference resistor and the channel voltage drop in the probe channel, and then analysing the change in probe channel voltage value from reference voltage drop and channel voltage drop. The output module outputs the results of the target material's analysis based on the voltage value change.

METHODOLOGY

The waterfall model utilised in the study approach is depicted in Figure 3. The purpose, objectives, and scope of the study for the *Leptospira* detection system were identified during the planning phase. During the analysis phase, a study of the existing *Leptospira* detection system was undertaken to determine the system's shortcomings and advantages. In addition, voltammetry and potentiostat creation approaches were investigated. The portable potentiostat design procedure and the design of a microcontroller based *Leptospira* detection system were then completed in the design phase. Finally, a testing phase of the designed *Leptospira* detection system will be performed.

FIGURE 3: Waterfall model

Figure 4 shows the overall flow chart of the research methodology designed for this study. Initially, a planning and analysis process was performed to identify the voltammetry techniques used, and to study the portable potentiostats used in electrochemical studies. Next, based on the research done, a portable potentiostat based on an Arduino microcontroller was designed. Then, an Arduino microcontroller program was constructed to be able to supply voltage based on the results of the study (Jurait et al., 2018). Subsequently, automatic Leptospira detection programming based on voltage versus current graph data obtained from the study results (Jurait et al., 2018) was constructed. Finally, a smartphone app was developed to display leptospira detection results.

FIGURE 4: Flow chart of research methodology

Portable potentiostat design

Proteus Design Suite was used to design the portable potentiostat used in this study. This software was used to construct the potentiostat circuit as well as simulate the microcontroller with the circuit that was designed. The circuit has been designed in two stages to achieve the research's objective precisely. The supply of voltage to the counter electrode is the first stage. An active low pass filter converts a PWM digital signal to an analogue voltage, an inverting amplifier converts the analogue signal to an inverting analogue signal. The signal is then converted back to its original polarity and buffer output by a second inverting amplifier. The feedback component from the reference electrode via the voltage follower amplifier is included in this buffer

level. The input impedance of the reference

electrode is considerably increased by this feedback signal, which reduces reverse current flow.

The second stage is the current reading from the working electrode, which includes a transimpedance amplifier and a voltage follower that delivers the value of the received current to the microcontroller's ANALOG INPUT pin as a voltage. The portable potentiostat circuit designed in this study is shown in Figure 5. The Arduino Uno microcontroller board is used to control the voltage and collect data in this potentiostat design. The voltage supply circuit uses OP177A which is a single op-amp, and the current reading circuit uses LM324 which is a quad op-amp. The Arduino Uno board runs a program that allows performing linear sweep voltammetry for the detection of the presence of leptospira. In this circuit, contains an LCD board, an oscilloscope and a serial monitor to obtain the circuit results.

FIGURE 5: Portable potentiostat circuit

The Arduino Uno board transmits the signal in the form of pulse width modulation (PWM) and for linear voltammetry sweep experiments, this PWM signal is sent to the counter electrode for a redox reaction. Since the PWM signal is in digital form, it needs to be converted to analog form, for that purpose, an active low pass filter circuit is used. This circuit contains resistors, capacitors and voltage follower amplifiers. In this type of filter arrangement, the input signal (VIN) is applied to a series combination (both Resistor and Capacitor) but the output signal (VOUT) is only taken in through the capacitor. Equation below is to calculate the output voltage for a resistor (R) and a capacitor (C) connected in series. (f) is the frequency of the PWM signal transmitted from pin 10 of the Arduino which is 490Hz. The values of R and C, R = 10KΩ and C = 10uF.

$$V_{OUT} = V_{IN} \times \frac{X_C}{\sqrt{R^2 + X_C^2}} ; X_C = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi f C}}$$

Figure 6 shows the active low pass filter used in the circuit.

FIGURE 6: Active low pass filter

The inverting amplifier circuit utilised in this study's portable potentiostat circuit is shown in Figure 7. Open loop amplifier operation has a very high DC gain. To minimise and adjust the overall gain of the amplifier, connect an appropriate resistor across the amplifier from the output terminal back to the reverse input terminal. This produces and exerts a negative feedback effect, which results in a highly stable working amplifier-based system. The technique of giving a little portion of the output signal back to the input is known as negative feedback. The output signal must be linked to the negative terminal or the op-amp boost input through a feedback resistor called R_f to provide negative feedback. Because the inverting input terminal will be the sum of the input voltage plus the negative feedback voltage designated as the peak point, the signal will be different from the real input voltage. As a result, an input resistor must be used to separate the true input signal from the reverse input signal, R_{in} . The non-inverse positive input is connected to a compensation resistor to compensate for the input bias current between the two inputs in the op-amp. It works to make the voltage drop to zero.

Figure 7: Inverting amplifier

A transimpedance amplifier is a current to voltage converter. The transimpedance amplifier circuit is a simple reverse amplifier with negative feedback. A feedback resistor is connected between the output

terminals inverting the amplifier as shown in Figure 8.

FIGURE 8: Transimpedance amplifier

The op-Amp input current will be zero due to its high input impedance. Therefore, the current from the current source must pass through the resistor (R_f) completely. The current from the current source is (I_{IN}). The output voltage (V_{OUT}) of the op-Amp can be calculated using equation below.

$$V_{OUT} = -I_{IN} \times R_f$$

The transimpedance amplifier circuit Figure 8 uses a generic low power amplifier LM324. Resistors and capacitors are connected to the feedback path. The LM324 amplifier is connected in a negative feedback configuration. The negative input pin is connected to the resistor and the feedback capacitor, the positive pin is connected to earth.

Leptospira Detection System

To design an effective Leptospira detection system, the microcontroller connected to the potentiostat must be programmed to run smoothly after the circuit is designed. As shown in Figure 9, the first level of programming is to digitally supply voltage to the potentiostat via PWM, the second is Leptospira detection programming, and the third is to develop a smartphone app as a display screen displaying current values from leptospira reactions with biosensor, as well as detection results.

FIGURE 9: Programming

The Arduino Uno microcontroller's PWM voltage is 5V, while the DAC can deliver voltages between 0 and 5V. As a result, to supply the voltage, the Arduino uno must be programmed using the PWM table. The detection system in this study should be supplied with a voltage range of 1.0V to 4.0V with a 0.5V step. The truth tables for the PWM-based DAC utilized in this work to supply the voltage are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: DAC Truth Table

Voltage (V)	PWM level
1.0	51
1.5	76.5
2.0	102
2.5	127.5
3.0	153
3.5	178.5
4.0	204

The comparison program is an important element in the leptospira detection system. Figure 10 shows the flow chart developed for Arduino uno programming to complement this system. Initially, the current data obtained from the graph shown as in Figure 2 will be recorded into the Arduino uno. In this study, a comparison of the current values that determined the presence of leptospira bacteria was performed with a range of $\pm 20\%$ margin as shown in Table 2.

FIGURE 10: Flow chart of Leptospira detection system

Table 2: list of leptospira detection current values by range $\pm 20\%$ margin

Voltage (V)	INPUT 0.2*INPUT (min) (mA)	INPUT (mA)	INPUT 0.2*INPUT (max) (mA)
1.0	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.5	0.00016	0.0002	0.00024
2.0	0.00032	0.0004	0.00048
2.5	0.00064	0.0008	0.00096
3.0	0.00104	0.0013	0.00156
3.5	0.00152	0.0019	0.00228
4.0	0.002	0.0025	0.003

After that, the program to supply voltage with range 1.0V- 4.0V will be uploaded. The current values from the study results (Jurait et al., 2018) are supplied to the working electrodes of the potentiostat circuit as a simulation of the leptospira reaction with the biosensor. This current is sent to the Arduino analog input pin in the form of a voltage after passing through the transimpedance amplifier. After the Arduino receives the current value, it will compare the current value with the previously recorded current data. In this comparison, if the two data are matched, are within the set range, the LCD will display the sign "BACTERIA IS PRESENT", otherwise if the two data do not match, the LCD will display the sign "BACTERIA IS NOT PRESENT".

In addition to the LCD board, a prototype user interface was developed to display results from decision -making performed by the Arduino. The developed mobile applications are named as LEPTOSPIRA DETECTION-apps, which function to (1) display the current values of leptospira and biosensor reaction currents; (2) displays the decision made by the Arduino, namely "BACTERIA PRESENT" or "BACTERIA NOT PRESENT". By using "MIT App Inventor", the design process is divided into two phases, namely the design of the user interface using the Component Designer and the implementation of programming logic using the Block Editor. As shown in Figure 11, this developed application is coded to connect to the Arduino uno utilizing a Bluetooth module. An Arduino uno, an Arduino HC-05 Bluetooth module, and a smartphone are the components and equipment used in this system.

FIGURE 11: Arduino Bluetooth module used for connection to applications

Bluetooth protocol is used by the LEPTOSPIRA DETECTION-apps to communicate with the bluetooth, thus the user must know the Bluetooth name of the module and the connection state. Figure 12 depicts the connection flow chart for the Leptospira detection system using Bluetooth technology. Figure 13 shows the Component Designer, an Android application user interface screen created for this study's leptospira detection system.

FIGURE 12: Flow chart of smartphone apps

FIGURE 13: LEPTOSPIRA DETECTION-apps user interface screen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Portable Potentiostat

The PWM signal is in digital form, it is converted to analog form with an RC filter. To configure the RC, the RC analysis tool is used as shown in Figure 14. Figure 15 shows the transient analysis graph for the voltage values of 1.0V, 1.5V, 2.0V, 2.5V, 3.0V, 3.5V and 4.0V, for the conversion response complete within 0.3 seconds. Figure 16 shows the results of the active low pass filter, analog voltage value is successfully converted from the PWM signal in the simulation.

FIGURE 14: RC analysis tool

After the PWM signal is converted to an analog value, a voltage flows through two inverting amplifiers and subsequently to the counter electrode. Figure 17 shows the voltage supplied to the counter electrode in a circuit. It is found that the voltage at the counter electrode is equal to the output voltage of the active low pass filter.

FIGURE 15: Transient analysis graph: (a) 1.0V (b) 1.5V (c) 2.0V (d) 2.5V (e) 3.0V (f) 3.5V (g) 4.0V

FIGURE 16: The results of the active low pass filter

FIGURE 17: Voltage supplied to counter electrode

Figure 18 shows a current receiving circuit that receives a current value from a working electrode. In this simulation the current value is supplied with a DC current source and labeled as the source current, I_S . Because the value of the current received from the working electrode is too low in micro units, this current value cannot be converted to a voltage value that can be read by the ANALOG INPUT pin of the microcontroller. Therefore, the potentiostat of this study uses an additional resistor known as a reflection resistor. This resistor is supplied with (-5V) to obtain the reference current, I_{REF} . This I_{REF} value is added to the I_S value to produce the input current, I_{IN} . The I_{IN} value will enter the negative terminal of the transimpedance amplifier. This I_{IN} can be calculated by equation below.

$$I_{IN} = -I_{REF} + I_S$$

FIGURE 18: Current receiving circuit

Refer to equation below,

$$V_{OUT} = -I_{IN} \times R_{F2}$$

V_{OUT} can be calculated from the I_{IN} current passing through the R_{F2} resistor on the transimpedance amplifier. As shown in Figure 18, V_{OUT} will flow through the voltage follower amplifier circuit and exit as V_{OUT2} , it is read by pin A0 ANALOG INPUT of the microcontroller. Table 3 shows the range of voltage values, V_{OUT2} based on $\pm 20\%$ margin of input current value received for comparison in the microcontroller.

Table 3: List of accepted V_{OUT2} voltage value ranges

INPUT - 0.2*INPUT (min) (mA)	INPUT (mA)	INPUT + 0.2*INPUT (max) (mA)
V_{OUT2} (max)	V_{OUT2}	V_{OUT2} (min)
2.51145	2.51145 (0.00mA)	2.51145
2.50954	2.50907 (0.0002mA)	2.50859
2.50763	2.50668 (0.0004mA)	2.50573
2.50382	2.50191 (0.0008mA)	2.50000
2.49904	2.49594 (0.0013mA)	2.49283
2.49331	2.49978 (0.0019mA)	2.48424
2.48758	2.48161 (0.0025mA)	2.47565

The linear voltage supply in the form of pulse width modulation (PWM) is generated through the use of the `analogWrite ()` program in the Arduino microcontroller. The `analogWrite ()` function is to specify the duty cycle for the PWM signal. The PWM duty cycles produced in this study are 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 70% and 80%. The PWM linear voltage should be generated based on the

linear sweep voltammetry of the study results (Jurait

et al., 2018). Figure 19 shows the PWM signal generated from the Arduino in the simulation for the voltages of 1.0V, 1.5V, 2.0V, 2.5V, 3.0V, 3.5V and 4.0V.

FIGURE 19: Simulation image of PWM signal from Arduino: (a) 1.0V (b) 1.5V (c) 2.0V (d) 2.5V (e) 3.0V (f) 3.5V (g) 4.0V

Leptospira detection system simulation

Table 4 shows the ADC levels based on the voltage value (V_{OUT2}) read by the Arduino microcontroller. This can be derived from the use of the `analogRead ()` program in Arduino. The `analogRead ()` function is to read the voltage value from pin A0 of the Analog Input. The Arduino board contains a 10-bit analog to digital converter (ADC). This means it will map the input voltage between 0 and the operating voltage (5V) to an integer value between 0 and 1023 using equation below.

$$ADC\ LEVEL = V_{OUT2} \times \frac{1023}{5}$$

Table 4: ADC level according to V_{OUT2}

INPUT - 0.2*INPUT (min)		INPUT		INPUT + 0.2*INPUT (max)	
$V_{OUT2(max)}$	ADC LEVEL	$V_{OUT2(V)}$	ADC LEVEL	$V_{OUT2(min)}$	ADC LEVEL
2.51145	513	2.51145	513	2.51145	513
2.50954	513	2.50907	512	2.50859	512
2.50763	512	2.50668	511	2.50573	511
2.50382	511	2.50191	511	2.50000	510
2.49904	510	2.49594	510	2.49283	509
2.49331	509	2.49978	508	2.48424	508
2.48758	508	2.48161	507	2.47565	506

The leptospira detection system program was constructed based on the ADC level in Table 4. The digit value of this ADC is the range of input values received based on the range of $\pm 20\%$ margin. Figure 20 and Figure 21 are the simulation results of the Leptospira detection system for 1.0V and 1.5V voltages. The LCD board display shows “BACTERIA IS PRESENT” if the current value, IS from the DC current source matches the current value recorded in the Arduino, otherwise the Arduino displays “BACTERIA IS NOT PRESENT” if it does not match. The Arduino can determine the presence of bacteria based on a comparison of the current data recorded in the Arduino with the received current data. For this simulation the current value supply is from a DC current source. For current values from DC current sources that exceed the range, Arduino will decide that the presence of bacteria is negative by displaying “BACTERIA IS NOT PRESENT” on the LCD board.

FIGURE 20: Simulation results of Leptospira 1.0V detection system for input current: (a) 0.000mA (b) 0.0002mA

FIGURE 21: Simulation results of 1.5V Leptospira detection system for input current: (a) 0.00022mA (b) 0.0008mA

Leptospira detection apps

Once the designed application is completed, the application download package (Android APK file) can be generated with the ‘Build’ option in the web application. The APK file can be downloaded by generating a QR code and scanning the code for download in the phone, or by choosing to save the APK to a computer then download it manually on the phone. The size of the built -in application is 10.16MB.

The first phase of testing was done by checking whether the phone application could connect to the HC-05 Arduino Bluetooth module using Bluetooth. Figure 22 shows the results of a Bluetooth connection. Once the application and Arduino are connected, the next phase is to test the application to display the input current value in the Arduino entered through the *SERIAL MONITOR* to make a comparison with the current value recorded in the Arduino and the result showing the presence of bacteria with “BACTERIA PRESENT” or vice versa “BACTERIA NOT PRESENT”. An example of the test process is illustrated in. Figure 23 which shows that when the input current value matches the range of current values recorded in the Arduino, the application displays the input current value and the Arduino result “BACTERIA PRESENT”. Figure 24 shows the application displaying “BACTERIA NOT PRESENT” when the input current value does not match the recorded current range.

FIGURE 22: Bluetooth connection status

FIGURE 23: The application displays “BACTERIA PRESENT” when the current value is in the range of Leptospira presence

FIGURE 24: The application displays “BACTERIA NOT PRESENT” when the current value is outside the range of Leptospira presence

CONCLUSION

A portable biosensor reader was successfully designed in this study. All three of the desired

objectives were proven to be successful. Linear sweep voltammetry has been discovered as an electroanalytic method for application in the construction of leptospira detection systems (LSV). The designed potentiostat receives the provided voltage in a linear form. The current at the working electrode is measured when the voltage between the counter electrode and the reference electrode is swept linearly during a fixed time interval in linear sweep voltammetry. This is an effective method for the detection of leptospira.

An Arduino microcontroller and multiple circuits comprising an operational amplifier are used to design the voltametric potentiostat. Active low pass filters, inverting amplifiers, transimpedance amplifiers, and non-inverting amplifiers, commonly known as voltage followers, are among the operating amplifier circuits employed. The Arduino's PWM signal is successfully converted to an analogue voltage form, which is then provided to the counter electrode. The current reading from the working electrode can be fed into the Arduino by converting current to voltage, making the Analog pins more understandable.

An on-site leptospira detection system is designed with Arduino microcontroller used was programmed based on the PANI Fe-Al biosensor specifications to detect the presence of leptospira in detail. The developed smartphone app can display leptospira presence and decision making made by Arduino.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by grants GUP-2020-014. The authors would like to thank to the Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia for supporting this project.

REFERENCES

Adler, B., & de la Peña Moctezuma, A. (2010). Leptospira and leptospirosis. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 140(3–4), 287–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2009.03.012>

Azizi, S., Kheirandish, R., & Rahimi, E. (2014). Comparison of polymerase chain reaction and Warthin-Starry techniques to detect *Leptospira* spp. in kidneys of slaughtered cattle. *The Onderstepoort Journal of Veterinary Research*, 81(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ojvr.v81i1.821>

Benacer, D., Who, P. Y., Zain, S. N. M., Amran, F., & Thong, K. L. (2013). Pathogenic and saprophytic *Leptospira* species in water and soils from selected urban sites in peninsular Malaysia. *Microbes and Environments*, 28(1), 135–140. <https://doi.org/10.1264/jsme2.ME12154>

Costa, F., Hagan, J. E., Calcagno, J., Kane, M., Torgerson, P., Martinez-Silveira, M. S., Stein, C., Abela-Ridder, B., & Ko, A. I. (2015). Global Morbidity and Mortality of Leptospirosis: A Systematic Review. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 9(9), 0–1. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0003898>

Jampasa, S., Lae-ngee, P., Patarakul, K., Ngamrojanavanich, N., Chailapakul, O., & Rodthongkum, N. (2019). Electrochemical immunosensor based on gold-labeled monoclonal anti-LipL32 for leptospirosis diagnosis. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 142(May), 111539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2019.111539>

Jurait, J., Abdullah, H., Bejo, S. K., & Yahya, I. (2018). *nanocomposite thin films for identification of pathogenic Leptospira*. 1515–1528.

Kaur, H., & Shorie, M. (2019). Nanomaterial based aptasensors for clinical and environmental diagnostic applications. *Nanoscale Advances*, 1(6), 2123–2138. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9na00153k>

Meloni, G. N., Profesor, A., & Prestes, L. (2016). *Building a Microcontroller Based Potentiostat: A Inexpensive and Versatile Platform for Teaching Electrochemistry and Instrumentation*. 1320–1322. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.5b00961>

Nagraik, R., Kaushal, A., Gupta, S., Dhar, P., Sethi, S., & Kumar, D. (2019). Optimized DNA-based bioassay for *Leptospira* interrogans detection: a novel platform for leptospirosis diagnosis. *3 Biotech*, 9(7), 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-019-1815-4>

Scholz, F. (2015). Voltammetric techniques of analysis: the essentials. *ChemTexts*, 1(4), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40828-015-0016-y>

Thakur, B., Amarnath, C. A., Mangoli, S. H., & Sawant, S. N. (2015). Polyaniline nanoparticle based colorimetric sensor for monitoring bacterial growth. *Sensors and Actuators, B: Chemical*, 207(Part A), 262–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2014.10.045>

Vasconcellos, F. A., Coutinho, M. L., da Silva, É. F., Fernandes, C. P. H., Monte, L. G., Seyffert, N., Dellagostin, O. A., & Aleixo, J. A. G. (2010). Testing different antigen capture ELISA formats for detection of *Leptospira* spp. in human blood serum. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 104(4), 259–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trstmh.2009.10.005>